

**SPECIAL STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC ROLE
OF A FOREIGN WORD IN THE TITLE**

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the important role of the headline in print media and the pragmatics it defines. The author makes an attempt to determine the stylistic, structural, semantic and aesthetic role of a foreign word in the title in a pragmatic aspect.

Keywords: title, text, foreign word, communicative influence, pragmatic attitudes.

One of the most important structural components that organize the text in printed publications is the title [1]. This is a structural and semantic element that carries both a stylistic and aesthetic load. The heading reveals especially strong, and in most cases far from simple, connections with the text, its deep semantic and aesthetic attitudes. The title of a literary work is both a code and a hint. This is the starting point from which the perception begins, but not always the creation) of the work, and the final, logical an expected point to which the interested reader inevitably returns. The heading pragmatically characterizes the entire text and presents it to the addressee as a kind of social identifier, giving an idea of the deep meaning of the entire text, of aesthetic and at the same time pragmatic attitudes. The special role of the title is often emphasized by a foreign word, which in a certain context gives bright connotations, pragmatic meanings, because "we are on the way to cultural bilingualism" [2, p. 12]. Compare: The title is the starting point for the figurative perception of the events that interested the reader. Newspaper headlines are an element of the situation of communicative influence between the author and the reader. It is known that there is an opinion about the speech statement as an action leading to the intended result [6, p. 212]. At present, "the stereotype of speech behavior itself has changed" [3, p. 236]. Communication between the author and the reader is not limited to "an elementary transfer of information, but involves a deep social content" [4, p. 314].The title with the use of a foreign word is polyreferential, as it is connected both with the text of the printed article, and with a different vision of the world, with a different national culture, with the linguistic personality of the journalist-author. Most of all, exoticisms and spaghetti inclusions are used in the so-called business press, which "forms a system of associations of linguistic thinking" in the reader [5, p. 157]. Newspaper headlines are an element of the situation of communicative influence

between the author and the reader. Their communication is not limited to the elementary transfer of information, but involves a deep social content. The verbal impact of the title is programmed for the calculated effect - not so much for the perlocutionary effect, but for the result of the impact on the reader (we do not know this, and we cannot assert that the reader's reactions are unambiguous), but for the communicative intention of the author, expressed in speech and recognized by the interlocutor-reader. The pragmatic goal of any heading is to achieve a result (to force the reader to share emotions, to think in line with the ideas of the author and, at the same time, to amaze the reader's imagination with an unexpected topic, a sensation). The title is both part of the text and a pre-text signal. And at the pre-text level, the title performs the task of attracting the reader, influencing his emotional and intellectual spheres. However, the meaning of the title is revealed only in the process of reading the text - then the informative function of the title is realized. The reader becomes more and more aware, because "the desire to acquire new knowledge is a natural human need" [6, p. 419]. The headline is pre-programmed to manipulate consciousness and to have some kind of communicative-situational effect. The pragmatic meanings in the headlines are especially pronounced during presidential election campaigns - these are the so-called "processes of activating public consciousness" [4, p. nineteen]. Thus, the ultimate pragmatic goal of any headline is to get a result, to evoke certain emotions in the reader. The title becomes not only a part of the text, but also, undoubtedly, a pre-text signal. At the pre-text level, the title attracts the reader's attention and affects his intellectual sphere.

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